

Current knowledge of Diaporthales (Ascomycota) in Bulgaria

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Received 31 July 2006 / Accepted 23 August 2006

Abstract. The known data on the diversity of the Diaporthales in Bulgaria are summarized and briefly discussed. For each taxon, the distribution throughout the country along with the literature sources referring to it and the herbarium acronym of the kept specimens are given. The information about the anamorphs of some diaporthalean species is also included. The species distribution by floristic regions is presented in a table.

Key words: ascomycetes, Bulgaria, Diaporthaceae, fungal diversity, Gnomoniaceae, Melanconidaceae, Valsaceae

Introduction

The information about fungi belonging to the Diaporthales and occurring in the Balkan Peninsula has been published in monographs or lists from Romania (Sandu-Ville 1971; Bontea 1985–1986) and Greece (Pantidou 1973). In Bulgaria, the diaporthalean fungi are still poorly known and no checklists have been made up to date. The aim of this paper is to summarize the existing data on species diversity and distribution of known representatives of the Diaporthales throughout the country.

Materials and Methods

This overview includes data obtained from the available mycological literature as well as information based on the specimens of the Mycological Collection of the Institute of Botany, Sofia (SOMF). Bulgarian specimens of the Diaporthales, preserved in some foreign collections, are also included. Some unpublished records and results of the senior author's field studies are also presented. The specimens supporting these records are kept in SOMF. The numbers (from 1 to 20), used for the floristic regions, follow the floristic division of the country, presented in Table 1. The abbreviation [n] is used for species, previously published from Bulgaria but lacking detailed locality information. Doubtful records are not included in the text. The system used for the families and genera within the order follows Merezhko & Smyk (1991), adopted to the latest *Outline of Ascomycota* (Eriksson 2006). In addition, taxonomic studies and contributions on the

diaporthalean fungi have been used (Barr 1978, 1990, 1991; Monod 1983; Spielman 1985; etc.).

Diaporthales

Gnomoniaceae G. Winter

Apiognomonium acerina (Starbäck) M. Monod, Sydowia, Beih. 9: 63, 1983.

On *Acer platanoides* L. [8] (Stoykov unpubl.; SOMF), [16] (Fakirova 1994; SOMF).

A. alniella (P. Karst.) Höhn., Hedwigia 62: 49, 1921.

On *Alnus incana* (L.) Moench [16] (Stoikov 2002a; SOMF).

A. errabunda (Roberge) Höhn., Ann. Mycol. 16: 51, 1918 (Syn.: *Gnomonia errabunda* (Roberge) Auersw.).

On *Castanea sativa* Mill. [16] (Stoikov 2002c), *Fagus sylvatica* L. [4, 8, 15, 16, 17] (Sameva 1982; Fakirova 1996; Stoykov unpubl.; SOMF), *F. sylvatica* L. subsp. *moesiaca* (K. Malý) Hjelmq. [4, 16] (SOMF), *Quercus frainetto* Ten. [16] (SOMF), *Q. rubra* L. [6] (Stoykov 2005a; SOMF), *Tilia cordata* Mill., *T. platyphyllos* Scop. [6, 8] (Stoykov unpubl.; SOMF).

A. erythrostroma (Pers. : Fr.) Höhn., Ann. Mycol. 16: 51, 1918 (Syn.: *Gnomonia erythrostroma* (Pers. : Fr.) Auersw.)

On *Prunus armeniaca* L. [2] (Dobrev 1983), *P. cerasifera* Ehrh. [16] (Stoykov unpubl.; SOMF).

A. fakirovae Stoykov, Mycotaxon 92: 459, 2005.

On *Quercus cerris* L. [16] (Stoikov & Fakirova 2001, as *Gnomonia clavulata* Ellis; Stoykov 2005b; SOMF).

A. ostryae (De Not.) M. Monod, Sydowia, Beih. 9: 50, 1983.

On *Ostrya carpinifolia* Scop. [11, 17, 18] (Malkoff 1906; Stoykov 2000; Stoykov 2005a; BPI, SOMF).

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- A. petiolicola* (Fuckel) M. Monod, Sydowia, Beih. 9: 64, 1983.
On *Tilia tomentosa* Moench [6, 16] (Stoikov & Fakirova 2001; Stoikov 2005a; SOMF).
- A. veneta* (Sacc. & Speg.) Höhn., Ann. Mycol. 16: 51, 1918.
On *Platanus* spp. [6, 10] (Stoikov unpubl.; SOMF).
Anamorph: *Gloeosporium nervisequum* (Fuckel) Sacc. [6] (Rosnev 1981).
- Cryptodiaporthe apiculata* (Wallr.) Petr., Ann. Mycol. 19: 177, 1921.
On *Salix appendiculata* Vill. (= *S. grandifolia* Ser.) [5] (Hruby 1931).
- C. salicina* (Curr.) Wehm., Univ. Michigan Stud., Sci. Ser. 9: 194, 1933.
On *Salix* spp. [5, 8] (Sameva 1985; SOMF).
- Diaporthella aristata* (Fr. : Fr.) Petr., Ann. Mycol. 22: 30, 1924 (Syn.: *Diaporthe exasperans* Nitschke).
On *Betula pendula* Roth [17] (Fakirova 1982, 1997; SOMF).
- Gnomonia alni-viridis* Podl.-Růž. & Svrček, Česká Mycol. 24(3): 129, 1970.
On *Alnus viridis* (Chaix) DC. [15] (Stoikov 2002b; SOMF).
- G. amoena* (Nees : Fr.) Ces. & De Not., Comment. Soc. Crittog. Ital. 1(4): 232, 1863.
On *Corylus avellana* L. [14, 15, 16] (Fakirova 1993a; Stoikov & Fakirova 2001; Stoikov 2002c; SOMF).
- G. amygdalinae* Fuckel, Jahrb. Nassauischen Vereins Naturk. 21-22: 121, 1869.
On *Euphorbia amygdaloides* L. [8] (Stoikov & Fakirova 2001; SOMF).
- G. betulina* Vleugel, Svensk Bot. Tidskr. 11: 305, 1917.
On *Betula pendula* Roth [4, 6, 8, 9, 15, 16] (Fakirova 1997; Stoikov 2005a, unpubl.; BPI, SOMF, WI).
- G. cerastis* (Riess) Ces. & De Not., Comment. Soc. Crittog. Ital. 1(4): 233, 1863 (Syn.: *G. aesculi* Oudem.).
On *Acer platanoides* L. [1] (Stoikov & Fakirova 2001; SOMF), *A. pseudoplatanus* L. var. *villosum* (C. Presl) Parl. [6, 16] (Stoikov & Fakirova 2001; BPI, SOMF, WI), *Aesculus hippocastanum* L. [6, 8] (Stoikov & Fakirova 2001; Stoikov 2002c; BILAS, SOMF, WI), *Fagus orientalis* Lipsky [20] (Stoikov unpubl.; SOMF), *Quercus* spp. [1] (Stoikov & Fakirova 2001), [4, 6, 16] (SOMF), herbaceous stem [16] (Sameva 1978; SOMF).
- G. comari* P. Karst., Mycol. Fenn. 2: 122, 1873.
On *Agrimonia eupatoria* L. [4, 5, 6, 11, 16, 18, 20] (Fakirova 1993c; Stoikov 2000; Stoikov 2005a, unpubl.; SOMF, WI), *Filipendula ulmaria* (L.) Maxim. [8] (Stoikov 2000; SOMF), *F. vulgaris* Moench. [6] (Stoikov 2002c; SOMF), *Geum urbanum* L. [4] (Stoikov unpubl.; BPI, SOMF), *Potentilla reptans* L. [6] (Stoikov 2005a; SOMF), *Rubus caesius* L. [6] (Stoikov 2002c; SOMF).
- G. ditopa* (Fr. : Fr.) M. Monod, Sydowia, Beih. 9: 88, 1983 (Syn.: *Ditopella ditopa* (Fr. : Fr.) J. Schröt.).
On *Alnus glutinosa* (L.) Gaertn. [8, 16] (Fakirova 1998; Stoikov 2002a; SOMF), *A. incana* (L.) Moench [14] (Fakirova 1982; SOMF).
- G. gei* Pat. & Doass., Tab. Anal. Fung. 5: 214, 1886.
On *Fragaria vesca* L. [6, 16] and *Geum urbanum* L. [6] (Stoikov 2002c; SOMF).
- G. gei-montani* Ranoj., Ann. Mycol. 8: 362, 1910.
On *Geum bulgaricum* Pančić [15] (Stoikov 2000; SOMF), *G. coccineum* Sibth. & Sm. [15] (Stoikov & Fakirova 2001; SOMF), *G. montanum* L. [8, 9] (Stoikov unpubl.; SOMF), *G. rhodopaeum* Stojanoff & Stef. [17] (Stoikov unpubl.; SOMF).
- G. geranii* Hollós, Anales Mus. Nat. Hung. 7: 52, 1909.
On: *Geranium sanguineum* L. [8, 16] (Stoikov 2000; Stoikov 2005a; BILAS, BPI, SOMF, WI), *Geranium* sp. [1] (Stoikov 2000).
- G. geranii-macrorrhizi* Fakirova, Mycotaxon 54: 329, 1995.
On *Geranium macrorrhizum* L. [4, 6, 8, 11, 12, 16, 17] (Fakirova 1995; Stoikov 2000, 2002c; Stoikov 2005a, unpubl.; BILAS, BPI, DAOM, SOMF, WI).
- G. gnomon* (Tode : Fr.) J. Schröt., Krypt.-Fl. Schles. 3(2): 390, 1894 (Syn.: *G. vulgaris* Ces. & De Not.).
On *Corylus avellana* L. [1, 4, 6, 8, 9, 11, 12, 14, 15, 16, 17, 20] (Sameva 1981; Fakirova 1982, as *G. setacea* (Pers. : Fr.) Ces. & De Not.; Fakirova 1996; Stoikov 2005a, unpubl.; SOMF, WI).
- G. leptostyla* (Fr. : Fr.) Ces. & De Not., Comment. Soc. Crittog. Ital. 1(4): 232, 1853.
On *Juglans regia* L. [1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 10, 11, 14, 16, 17, 18, 20] (Sameva 1978; Fakirova 1982; Tsanova & Rosnev 1979; Stoikov 2002c; Stoikov 2005a, unpubl.; BPI, BILAS, SOMF, WI).
Anamorph: *Marssonniella juglandis* (Lib.) Höhn. on *Juglans regia*, *J. nigra* L. [2, 6, 9, 16, 17, 18] (Malkoff 1905; Radoslavov 1914; Rosnev & Tsanova 1980; SOMF); *Melanconium juglandinum* Kunze on *Juglans regia* L. [19] (Tsanova & Rosnev 1976).
- G. nantensis* M. Monod, Sydowia, Beih. 9: 118, 1983.
On *Geranium* sp. [1] (Stoikov 2005a).
- G. nervisequa* (Wallr.) Fuckel, Jahrb. Nassauischen Vereins Naturk. 23-24: 122, 1870.
On *Alnus glutinosa* (L.) Gaertn. [1, 4, 8, 16, 20] (Stoikov 2002a; Stoikov 2005a, unpubl.; BPI, BILAS, SOMF, WI), *A. viridis* (Chaix) DC. [15] (Fakirova 1998), *Carpinus betulus* L. [4, 5, 6] (Stoikov 2002c; Stoikov 2005a), *Corylus avellana* L. [4, 16] (SOMF), *Juglans regia* L. [4, 6, 12] (Stoikov 2005a, unpubl.; SOMF).
- G. orientalis* M. Monod, Sydowia, Beih. 9: 122, 1983.
On *Euphorbia amygdaloides* L. [8] (Stoikov & Fakirova 2001; SOMF).
- G. palustris* M. Monod, Sydowia, Beih. 9: 120, 1983.
On stems of *Euphorbia* sp. [4] (Stoikov unpubl.).
- G. pseudoamoena* M. Monod, Sydowia, Beih. 9: 86, 1983.
On *Corylus avellana* L. [15, 16] (Stoikov 2002c; SOMF).
- G. rosae* Fuckel, Jahrb. Nassauischen Vereins Naturk. 23-24: 122, 1870.
On *Agrimonia eupatoria* L., *A. proceras* Wallr., *Rubus rivularis* Wirtg. & Mueller [16] (BILAS, SOMF); *Potentilla micrantha* Ramond ex DC. [4] (Stoikov 2002b; Stoikov 2005a; SOMF).
- G. rostellata* (Fr. : Fr.) Wehm., Canad. J. Res. 20: 572, 1942 (Syn.: *G. rubi* Rehm).
On *Rubus caesius* L. [15, 17] (Stoikov 2005a; SOMF), *Rubus* sp. [8, 17] (Fakirova 1978; Stoikov 2000; SOMF).
- G. setacea* (Pers. : Fr.) Ces. & De Not., Comment. Soc. Crittog. Ital. 1(4): 232, 1863.
On *Alnus glutinosa* [16] (Stoikov 2002a), *Castanea sativa* Mill. [11] (Stoikov unpubl.; SOMF), *Corylus avellana* L. [1, 4, 6, 7, 16, 17, 19, 20] (Stoikov unpubl.; SOMF), *Quercus cerris* L. [4, 5, 6, 16, 20] (Sameva 1982, as *Gnomonia inclinata* (Desm.) Auersw.; Stoikov 2005a, unpubl.;

- BPI, BILAS, SOMF, WI), *Q. dalechampii* Ten. [15] (Stoykov unpubl.), *Q. thracica* Stef. & Nedjalkov [6] (Stoykov unpubl.; SOMF), *Quercus* spp. [4, 6, 16] (Fakirova 1982; SOMF).
- G. tetraspora** G. Winter, *Hedwigia* 21: 148, 1872.
On *Euphorbia amygdaloides* L. [4, 8] (Stoikov & Fakirova 2001; Stoykov unpubl.; SOMF), *E. barrelieri* Savi [10] (Stoikov 2002c; BUCM), *E. cyparissias* L. [8, 16] (Stoikov & Fakirova 2001; SOMF), *E. esula* L. [6] (Stoikov 2002c; SOMF), *Euphorbia* sp. [9] (Stoikov & Fakirova 2001; SOMF).
- G. vallesiaca** M. Monod, *Sydowia*, *Beih.* 9: 132, 1983.
On *Epilobium angustifolium* L. [15] (Stoikov 2000; SOMF).
- Gnomoniella tubaeformis** (Tode : Fr.) Sacc., *Syll. Fung.* 1: 413, 1882.
On *Alnus glutinosa* (L.) Gaertn. [16] (Sameva 1981; Fakirova 1998; Stoikov 2002a; SOMF).
- Mamiania fimbriata** (Pers. : Fr.) Ces. & De Not., *Shema Sfer. Ital.*, p. 36, 1863 (Syn.: *Gnomoniella fimbriata* (Pers. : Fr.) Sacc.).
On *Carpinus betulus* L. [6, 15] (Malkoff 1910).
- Mamianiella coryli** (Batsch : Fr.) Höhn., *Ann. Mycol.* 16: 102, 1918 (Syn.: *Mamiania coryli* (Batsch : Fr.) Ces. & De Not.; *Gnomoniella coryli* (Batsch : Fr.) Sacc.).
On *Corylus avellana* L. [6, 15] (Malkoff 1910; Picbauer 1937; Christoff 1939), *C. maxima* Willd. [6, 15] (Malkoff 1910; Christoff 1939).
- Ophiognomonia melanostyla** (DC. : Fr.) Sacc. ex Berl., *Icon. Fung.* 2: 146, 1899 (Syn.: *Cryptoderis melanostyla* (DC. : Fr.) G. Winter).
On *Tilia* sp. [14] (Fakirova 1985; SOMF).
Note. Revision of a specimen from SOMF labelled as *C. melanostyla* revealed only perithecia, asci, and ascospores of *Gnomonia gnomon* on leaf of *Corylus avellana*.
- Ophiovalsa betulae** (Tul. & C. Tul.) Petr., *Sydowia* 19: 275, 1966 (Syn.: *Cryptospora betulae* Tul. & C. Tul.).
On *Betula pendula* Roth [8, 16] (Fakirova 1978, 1997; SOMF).
- O. suffusa** (Fr. : Fr.) Petr., *Sydowia* 19: 272, 1966 (Syn.: *Cryptospora suffusa* (Fr. : Fr.) Tul. & C. Tul.).
On *Alnus* sp. [15] (Fakirova 1985, 1998; SOMF), *Fagus* sp. [15] (Fakirova 1985).
- Plagiostoma alneum** (Fr. : Fr.) Arx, *Antonie van Leeuwenhoek Ned. Tijdschr. Hyd.* 17: 264, 1951.
On *Alnus glutinosa* (L.) Gaertn. [1, 4, 8, 16, 20] (Fakirova 1994, 1998; Stoikov 2002a, b; Stoikov 2005a, unpubl.; SOMF, WI), *A. incana* (L.) Moench [16] (SOMF).
- P. arnstadtense** (Auersw.) M. Monod, *Sydowia*, *Beih.* 9: 143, 1983 (Syn.: *P. rehmi* (Sacc.) Arx).
On *Carpinus betulus* L. [4, 5, 6, 8, 16, 17] (Fakirova 1993b; Stoikov 2000; Stoikov 2005a; SOMF), *C. orientalis* Mill. [4, 6, 16, 17] (Sameva 1981, as *Hypospila pustula* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Karst.; Stoikov 2005a; SOMF), *Ostrya carpinifolia* Scop. [11] (Stoikov 2000; SOMF).
- P. bavarium** (Rehm) M.E. Barr, *Mycol. Mem.* 7: 112, 1978.
On *Acer campestre* L. [1, 4, 6, 8, 16] (SOMF, WI), *A. hyrcanum* Fisch. & C.A. Mey. [8, 16] (SOMF), *A. pseudoplatanus* L. [4, 7, 15, 16] (Fakirova 1993a, b, c; Stoikov 2005a, unpubl.; SOMF).
- P. castanicolum** Fakirova, *Int. J. Mycol. Lichenol.* 5(3): 209, 1992.
On *Castanea sativa* Mill. [16] (Fakirova 1992; SOMF).
- P. inclinatum** (Desm.) M.E. Barr, *Mycol. Mem.* 7: 115, 1978.
On *Acer campestre* L. [1, 7, 16] (Stoikov 2000; Stoikov & Fakirova 2001; Stoikov unpubl.; SOMF), *A. heldreichii* Boiss. [15] (Stoikov unpubl.), *A. pseudoplatanus* L. [4, 6, 16] (SOMF).
- Diaporthaceae Höhn.**
- Allantoportha tessella** (Pers.) Petr., *Hedwigia* 62: 289, 1921 (Syn.: *Diaportha tessella* (Pers.) Rehm).
On *Salix* sp. [5] (Fakirova 1985; SOMF).
- Apioporthella vepris** (Delacr.) M.E. Barr, *Mycotaxon* 41: 288, 1991 (Syn.: *Apioportha vepris* (Delacr.) Wehm.; *Cryptodiaportha vepris* (Delacr.) Petr.).
On *Rubus caesius* L. [15] (Stoikov 2005a; SOMF), *R. idaeus* L. [5, 8, 15] (Fakirova 1978, 1982; Stoikov 2005a; SOMF), *Verbascum* sp. [8] (Sameva 1982; Stoikov 2005a; SOMF).
- Cryphonectria parasitica** (Murr.) M.E. Barr, *Mycol. Mem.* 7: 143, 1978 (Syn.: *Endothia parasitica* (Murr.) Auersw.).
On *Castanea sativa* Mill. [5, 11, 17, 20] (Petkov & Rosnev 2000, 2001).
- Diaportha angelicae** (Berk.) D.F. Farr & Castl., *Mycoscience* 44: 204, 2003.
On *Carum carvi* L. [6] (Rodeva & Gabler 2005; SOMF).
- D. carpini** (Pers.) Fuckel, *Jahrb. Nassauischen Vereins Naturk.* 23-24: 205, 1870.
On *Carpinus betulus* L. [5] (Fakirova 1982, 1993b; SOMF).
- D. crataegi** (Curr.) Nitschke ex Fuckel, *Jahrb. Nassauischen Vereins Naturk.* 23-24: 204, 1870.
On *Crataegus* sp. [5, 7] (Fakirova 1985; SOMF).
- D. eres** Nitschke, *Pyrenom. German.* 2: 245, 1870.
On *Betula pendula* Roth [17], *Prunus cerasus* L., *P. domestica* L. [1, 3], deciduous tree [5] (Sameva 1985; SOMF).
- D. fagi** Wehm., *Univ. Michigan Stud., Sci. Ser.* 9: 145, 1933.
On *Fagus sylvatica* L. [8, 16] (Fakirova 1994; Stoikov unpubl.; SOMF).
- D. idaeicola** (P. Karst.) Vesterg., *Bot. Not.*, p. 156, 1899.
On *Rubus idaeus* L. [15] (Hruby 1931).
- D. juglandina** (Fuckel) Nitschke, *Pyrenom. German.*, p. 281, 1870.
On *Juglans regia* L. [4, 14] (Fakirova 1978; Stoikov unpubl.; SOMF).
Anamorph: *Phomopsis juglandina* (Fuckel) Hohn. on *Juglans regia* L. [4] (Christoff & Christova 1936).
- D. leiphaemia** (Fr. : Fr.) Sacc., *Atti Soc. Veneto-Trent. Sci. Nat.* 2: 135, 1873.
On *Quercus* sp. [16] (Fakirova 1985).

D. oncostoma (Dubý) Fuckel, Jahrb. Nassauischen Vereins Naturk. 23-24: 205, 1870.

On *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. [4, 17] (Fakirova 1982; SOMF), deciduous trees [14] (Fakirova 1978, 1982; SOMF).

D. perniciosus Marchal & É.J. Marchal, Bull. Soc. Roy. Bot. Belgique 54: 117, 1921.

On *Prunus cerasus* L. [1], *P. domestica* L. [3] (Christoff 1934, as *Phomopsis* sp.), *Vitis vinifera* L. [n] (Vanev 1995).

D. pustulata (Desm.) Sacc., Syll. Fung. 1: 610, 1882 (Syn.: *Valsa pustulata* Auersw.).

On *Fagus sylvatica* L. [16] (Fakirova 1978; Fakirova & Sameva 1983).

Valsaceae Tul. & C. Tul.

Apioplagiostoma aceriferum (Cooke) M.E. Barr, Mycol. Mem. 7: 103, 1978.

On *Acer campestre* L. [1, 4, 16] (Stoikov 2000; Stoikov 2005a; BPI, SOMF, WI).

A. carpnicolum (Höhn.) M.E. Barr, Mycol. Mem. 7: 103, 1978.

On *Carpinus betulus* L. [4, 5, 8, 16] (Sameva 1981, 1982, as *Sphaerognomonia carpinea* Potebnia; Fakirova 1982, as *S. carpinea*; Fakirova 1993b, as *Gnomoniella carpinea* (Fr. : Fr.) M. Monod; Stoikov 2005a; SOMF, WI), *C. orientalis* Mill. [4, 16] (Stoikov 2005a; SOMF).

Ditopellina saccardiana (Traverso & Spessa) J. Reid & C. Booth, Canad. J. Bot. 45(9): 1481, 1967.

On *Fraxinus* sp. [16] (Stoikov 2005a; SOMF).

Hyospilina bifrons (Kunze & J.C. Schmidt : Fr.) Traverso, Fl. Ital. Crypt. 1: 495, 1913.

On *Quercus coccifera* L. [14] (Fakirova 1996; SOMF).

H. pustula (Pers. : Fr.) M. Monod, Sydowia, Beih. 9: 189, 1983.

On *Castanea sativa* Mill [8, 9, 11] (Stoikov unpubl.; SOMF), *Quercus cerris* L. [1, 20] (Stoikov unpubl.; SOMF) [3, 4, 16, 20] (Stoikov 2005a; SOMF, WI), *Q. dalechampii* Ten. [4, 7, 12, 15, 17, 20] (Stoikov 2005a, unpubl.; SOMF, WI) (SOMF), *Q. frainetto* Ten. [3, 4, 17, 18, 20] (Stoikov 2005a, unpubl.; SOMF, WI), *Q. pedunculiflora* C. Koch [4, 6, 8, 16, 18], *Q. polycarpa* Schur [20] (Stoikov unpubl.; SOMF), *Q. pubescens* Willd. [10] (Stoikov unpubl.; SOMF); *Q. robur* L. [5, 6, 16] (Stoikov 2005a; SOMF), *Q. rubra* L. [1, 4, 6, 8] (Stoikov 2005a; SOMF), *Q. virgiliana* Ten. [6, 16] (SOMF), *Quercus* sp. [8, 16] (Fakirova 1993a; Sameva 1981), deciduous trees (Fakirova 1993b).

H. rhodopea Bubák & Picb., Ann. Mycol. 35: 138, 1937 (as *Hyospila rhodopea*).

On *Prunus cerasifera* Ehrh. (*P. divaricata* Ledeb.) [17] (Picbauer 1937).

Leucostoma auerswaldii (Nitschke) Höhn., Mitt. Bot. Lab. TH Wien 5: 52, 1928 (Syn.: *Valsa auerswaldii* Nitschke).

On *Fagus sylvatica* L. [4, 16] (Fakirova 1978, 1985; Fakirova & Sameva 1983; SOMF), *Pyrus communis* L. [5] (Fakirova 1985).

(?) *L. massarianum* (De Not.) Höhn., Ber. Deutsch. Bot. Ges. 35: 637, 1917.

On *Rosa canina* L. [8] (Sameva 1982; SOMF).

Note. We did not succeed in finding any ascomata in the specimen kept in SOME.

L. nivea (Hoffm. : Fr.) Höhn., Mitt. Bot. Lab. TH Wien 5: 58, 1928 (Syn.: *Valsa nivea* (Hoffm.) Fr.).

On *Populus tremula* L., *Populus* sp. [2, 6, 8] (Hruby 1931; Fakirova 1985; SOMF, as *L. nivea* (Pers. : Fr.) Defago); *Juniperus* sp. [16] (SOMF), *Rosa* sp. [16] (Fakirova 1985, as *L. nivea* (Pers. : Fr.) Defago; SOMF).

L. personii (Nitschke) Höhn., Mitt. Bot. Lab. TH Wien 5: 60, 1928 (Syn.: *Valsa leucostoma* (Pers.) Fr.).

On *Prunus persica* (L.) Batsch [n], *P. spinosa* L. [5, 16] (Fakirova 1978; SOMF).

L. translucens (De Not.) Höhn., Mitt. Bot. Lab. TH Wien 5: 55, 1928.

On *Salix* sp. [6] (Sameva 1985; SOMF).

Sillia ferruginea (Pers. : Fr.) P. Karst, Mycol. Fenn. 2: 159, 1873.

On *Betula pendula* Roth [16] (Fakirova 1978; Fakirova & Sameva 1983; SOMF).

Valsa ambiens (Pers. : Fr.) Fr., Summa Veg. Scand., p: 412, 1849 (Syn.: *Cryptosporella populina* (Fuckel) Sacc.).

On *Acer* sp. [6] (Hruby 1931), *Betula pendula* Roth [8] (Fakirova 1997; SOMF), *Fraxinus* sp. [16] (Fakirova 1985; SOMF), *Malus domestica* Borkh. [4] (SOMF), *Populus* sp. [18] (Fakirova 1982), *Prunus spinosa* L. [16] (SOMF), *Pyrus* sp. [8] (SOMF), *Syringa vulgaris* L. [16] (Fakirova 1985; SOMF), deciduous tree [16] (SOMF).

V. ceratosperma (Tode : Fr.) Maire, Publ. Inst. Bot. 3(4): 20, 1937 (Syn.: *V. ceratophora* Tul. & C. Tul., *V. decorticans* Fr., *V. coronata* (Hoffm.) Fr.).

On *Fagus sylvatica* L. [16] (Fakirova & Sameva 1983; Fakirova 1985; SOMF), *Malus domestica* Borkh. [4] (SOMF), *Rubus* sp. [17] (Fakirova 1982; SOMF).

V. cincta (Fr. : Fr.) Fr., Summa Veg. Scand., p. 411, 1849 (Syn.: *Leucostoma cinctum* (Fr. : Fr.) Höhn.).

On *Prunus spinosa* L. [4] (Fakirova 1985; SOMF), *Rubus* sp. [17] (Fakirova 1982).

V. cypri (Tul.) Tul. & C. Tul., Select. Fung. Carpol. 2: 194, 1863.

On *Syringa vulgaris* L. [16] (SOMF), *Fraxinus* sp. [16] (Sameva 1985; SOMF).

V. fallax Nitschke in Fuckel, Jahrb. Nassauischen Vereins Naturk. 21-22: 200, 1869.

On *Cornus sanguinea* L. [17] (Fakirova 1982; SOMF).

V. intermedia Nitschke, Pyrenom. German., p. 199, 1870.

On *Quercus* sp. [16] (Fakirova 1985; SOMF).

V. salicina (Pers. : Fr.) Fr., Summa Veg. Scand., p. 412, 1849.

On *Salix* sp. [5] (Fakirova 1978; SOMF).

V. sordida Nitschke, Pyrenom. German. 2: 203, 1870.

On *Populus* sp. [8] (Fakirova 2004; SOMF).

Anamorph: *Cytospora chrysosperma* (Pers.) Fr. on *Populus alba* L. var. *canescens* Aiton [6] (Atanasov & Kovachevsky 1929).

V. viburni Fuckel, Jahrb. Nassauischen Vereins Naturk. 21-22: 201, 1869.

On *Viburnum lantana* L. [8] (Fakirova 2004; SOMF).

Table 1. Distribution of the taxa of Diaporthales in the floristic regions of Bulgaria

Region [number]	Gnomoniaceae										Diaporthaceae								Valsaceae					Melanconiaceae					Species per region	
	<i>Apiognomonia</i>	<i>Cryptodiaportha</i>	<i>Diaporthella</i>	<i>Gnomonia</i>	<i>Gnomoniella</i>	<i>Mamiania</i>	<i>Mamianiella</i>	<i>Ophiognomonia</i>	<i>Ophiovalsa</i>	<i>Plagiostoma</i>	Total	<i>Allantoportha</i>	<i>Apioporthelia</i>	<i>Cryphonectria</i>	<i>Diaportha</i>	Total	<i>Apioplagiostoma</i>	<i>Ditopellina</i>	<i>Hypospilina</i>	<i>Leucostoma</i>	<i>Sillia</i>	<i>Valsa</i>	<i>Valsella</i>	Total	<i>Apiosporopsis</i>	<i>Melanconis</i>	<i>Melogramma</i>	<i>Pseudovalsa</i>	<i>Sydowiella</i>	Total
Black Sea Coast [1]				7	3	10				3	2	2	1	1	2									2					0	14
Northeastern Bulgaria [2]	1			1		2										0				1				1					0	3
Danube Plain [3]						0						2	2	1	1									1					0	3
Forebalkan [4]	1			11		16			4	16									1	1		3		7	1			1	26	
Stara Planina Mts [5]		2		4	1	7	1	1	1	3	6	1	1	2	1	6			1	2	1	1	1	6		1		1	20	
Sofia region [6]	3			10		18			3	18						1			1	2	2	2	5	1				1	25	
Znepole region [7]				1		3			2	3						1			1	1	1	1	1	1				0	5	
Vitosha region [8]	2	1		13		20		1	3	20		1				2	1	1	2	2	3	3	7	1	2		1	4	33	
West Frontier Mts [9]				5		5				5						0			1				1					0	6	
Strouma Valley [10]	1			2		3				3						0			1				1					0	4	
Belasitsa Mt [11]	1			5		7		1	1	7		1				1			1	1	1	1	1	1			1	1	10	
Slavyanka Mt [12]				3		3				3						0			1	1			1					0	4	
Mesta Valley [13]				0		0				0						0							0					0	0	
Pirin Mts [14]				4		5				5						2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		2	10	
Rila Mts [15]	1	1		10		17		1	2	17						1			1	1	1	1	1	1			1	1	21	
Sredna Gora Mts [16]	6			15	1	28		1	5	28		2	1	1	3	3	2	1	1	3	1	4	12	1	2	1	1	5	48	
Rhodopi Mts [17]	2	1		6		10			1	10			1	2	3	5		2	2	3	3	3	5	1	1		1	2	20	
Thracian Plain [18]	1			2		3				3						0			1	1	1	1	2					0	5	
Toundzha hilly region [19]				1		1				1						0							0						0	1
Strandzha Mt [20]				6		7			1	7		1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	10	
Total	8	2	1	23	1	45	1	1	2	5	1	1	1	11	14	2	1	3	5	1	9	1	22	1	3	1	1	2	89	

Valsella nigroannuata Fuckel, Syll. Fung. 1: 160, 1837.

On *Salix* sp. [5] (Fakirova 1978; SOMF).

Melanconidaceae G. Winter

Apiosporopsis carpinea (Fr. : Fr.) Traverso, Syll. Fung. 22: 78, 1913 (Syn.: *Sphaerognomonia carpinea* (Fr. : Fr.) Potebnia; *Gnomoniella carpinea* (Fr. : Fr.) M. Monod).

On *Carpinus betulus* L. [8, 16] (Fakirova 1978, 1993b; Sameva 1982), *Quercus dalechampii* Ten. [8, 16] (SOMF), *Q. coccifera* L. [14] (SOMF), *Q. pedunculiflora* C. Koch [4, 6] (SOMF).

Note. The revision of a specimen from SOMF, published by Sameva (1982) from Sredna Gora Mt, revealed also *Apioplagoistoma carpincolum* (Höhn.) M.E. Barr.

Melanconis chrysostroma (Fr.) Tul. & C. Tul., Select. Fung. Carpol. 2: 125, 1863.

On *Carpinus betulus* L. [8, 16] (Fakirova 1985, 1993b; SOMF).

M. modonia Tul. & C. Tul., Select. Fung. Carpol., 2: 141, 1863.

Anamorph: *Coryneum modonium* (Sacc.) Griffon & Maubl. on *Castanea sativa* Mill. [5, 17, 20] (Rosnev & Zahov 1982).

M. stilbostoma (Fr. : Fr.) Tul. & C. Tul., Select. Fung. Carpol. 2: 115, 1863.

On *Betula pendula* Roth [8] (Fakirova 1978, 1997; SOMF), *Carpinus betulus* L. [16] (Fakirova 1993b; SOMF).

Melogramma spiniferum (Wallr.) De Not., Fung. Ital., p. 53, 1863.

On *Fagus sylvatica* L. [16] (Fakirova 1978).

Pseudovalsa lanciformis (Fr. : Fr.) Ces. & De Not., Comment. Soc. Crittog. Ital. 1: 206, 1863.

On *Fraxinus* sp. [16] (Fakirova 1985).

Sydowiella depressula (P. Karst.) M.E. Barr, Mycol. Mem. 7: 159, 1978.

On *Rubus idaeus* L. [8] (Stoikov 2002c; SOMF).

S. fenestrans (Duby) Petr., Ann. Mycol. 21: 30, 1923.

On *Epilobium angustifolium* L. [11, 15, 17] (Fakirova 1978; Stoikov 2005a; SOMF).

Excluded records:

Diaporthe sigma (Hoffm.) De Not. [= *Diatrype stigma* (Hoffm.) De Not.]

On twigs of *Carpinus betulus* L., *Quercus* sp. [8, 16, 17] (Fakirova 1978, 1982; SOMF).

Valsa prunastri (Pers.) Fr., Summa Veg. Scand, p. 411, 1949 [= *Eutypa lata* (Pers.) Tul. & C. Tul.].

On bark of *Prunus armeniaca* L., *P. avium* L. [3] (Kozarov 1908).

Conclusion

This overview includes 89 species belonging to 26 genera and 4 families. Most of the species belong to Gnomoniaceae (45 species), Valsaceae (22), Diaporthaceae (14), and

Melanconidaceae (8). The genus *Gnomonia* is richest in species (23), followed by *Diaporthe* (11), *Valsa* (9), *Apiognomonia* (8), *Plagiostoma* (5), and *Leucostoma* (5).

The country has been unequally investigated regarding the diaporthalean fungi in different floristic regions. For instance, the greatest number of species is recorded from Sredna Gora Mts (48), followed by Vitosha region (33), Forebalkan (26), Sofia region (25), Rila Mts (21), Stara Planina Mts (20) and Rhodopi Mts (20), Black Sea Coast (14), Belasitsa Mt (10), Pirin Mts (10), and Strandzha Mt (10). No data from the valley of River Mesta have been published (Table 1).

Acknowledgements. Comments on the MS by Dr Larissa Vasilyeva (Institute of Biology and Soil Science, Vladivostok, Russia) are kindly acknowledged. The senior author is grateful to Dr Ana Petrova and V. Goranova (Institute of Botany, Sofia) for supporting the field trips in 2004-2005 and to MSc B. Assyov for materials placed at his disposal. The study of C.M. Denchev was supported by the National Science Fund, Bulgarian Ministry of Education and Science (Project no. B-1302).

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